

The Tsallis Distribution and Temperature Variations/Fluctuations

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In (1), it is stated that a Tsallis distribution may describe a physical situation in which there are temperature variations (or even fluctuations). For example, in a heavy ion collision, various regions with different temperatures may be created with each representing its own Maxwell-Boltzmann $\exp(-e/T)$ equilibrium. Given this physical scenario, (1) fits the known Tsallis distribution: $\{ 1 - (1-q)e/T \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$ to $\int db F(b) \exp(-eb)$ where $b=1/T$. Based on their work in (2) using Mellin transformations, (1) suggests that $F(b)$ is the argument of a gamma function which it explicitly lists. In other words, the goal is to start with a priori knowledge of the Tsallis distribution and find an appropriate $F(b)$ which happens mathematically to be a gamma function integrand.

Here, we note that if instead of the Maxwell-Boltzmann weight, $\exp(-e/T)$, used in (1), a uniform distribution 1 is employed instead, one would have (using the result of (1)): $\int db f(b) = \Gamma(z+1) = z!$, where $z+1$ is the exponent in the gamma function argument. We suggest that the $z!$ factorial might have statistical significance on its own. In particular, the value of z is linked with $b_0 / (\sigma^2)$ - 2 ((1)). Here b_0 is the average $1/T_0$ over the regions with various temperatures and σ^2 , the variance of b . Given that one deals with square values in calculating variance, b_0 appears instead of $1/T$. It seems that the $z!$ interpretation of the gamma function may mean that ((1)) represents a number of "quanta" so to speak which may be arranged (permuted) $z!$ ways in order to create a statistical weight. If there is some physical/statistical relevance to this assumption, we argue that it serves as an a priori approach to deriving the Tsallis distribution. In other words, one does not have to fit the known Tsallis distribution to a gamma function integrand multiplied by $\exp(-e/T)$, but may choose the gamma function integrand a priori based on the idea of $z!$, thus obtaining the Tsallis distribution when one introduces the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-eb)$.

Tsallis Distribution and Mellin Transformation

The unnormalized Tsallis distribution, which may be obtained in numerous ways, is given by:

$$f(e) = \{ 1 - (1-q)e/T \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \quad ((2))$$

In (1), it is suggested that $f(e)$ Tsallis may be applied to a physical system with fluctuating temperature or different regions with different temperatures. Such a system could be created during a heavy ion collision. There would then be Maxwell-Boltzmann distributions and equilibria in each region with its own temperature T or $b=1/T$.

Given this physical scenario, (1) finds a function $F(b)$ such that:

$$\{ 1 - (1-q)e/T \}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} = \int db F(b) \exp(-e/T) \quad ((3))$$

(1) explicitly shows that $F(b)$ is given by:

$$F(b) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(a)} \left(\frac{a}{b_0}\right)^a b^{a-1} \exp(-ba/b_0)$$

$$\text{where } b_0 = b \text{ average, } a = 1/(q-1) = b_0^2 / \text{variance}(b) \quad ((4))$$

In (2), the authors of (1) argue for the above form based on a Mellin transformation. In other words, it is introduced due to the mathematical properties of the gamma function and not on any a priori statistical argument, it seems.

Attempt to Assign Statistical Meaning to the Gamma Function Argument

The main purpose of this note is to try to anticipate the gamma function form of $F(b)$. If this is possible, one may introduce $F(b)$ a priori without knowing the Tsallis distribution and hence deduce the distribution.

We begin with the well-known result for a gamma function:

$$\int_0^{\infty} t^{z+1} \exp(-t) dt = z! \quad ((5))$$

We note that in ((3)) one sees the presence of the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor $\exp(-e/T)$. If one had a uniform distribution instead, one would have the result:

$$\int db F(b) \quad ((6))$$

We ask if this integral should have any statistical significance.

The t^{z+1} term in ((4)) is related to $(ab/b_0)^{a-1}$, where a is alpha in (1).

Thus: $z+1 = a-1$ or $z = a-2 = b_0^2 / \text{variance}(b) - 2$ ((7)) Here b_0 is the average of $b = 1/T$.

In other words, the weight $F(b)$ is linked with $\{b_0^2 / \text{variance}(b) - 2\}!$ ((8))

In general, the physical quantity of interest is $b = 1/T$, but variance is a statistical quantity and so there is no reason for b_0^2 (squared values) not to have relevance. It is known that $z!$ represents the permutations of z objects. This factorial is used to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy expression: $\ln\{N! / \prod_i n_i!\}$. We suggest then that the factorial in ((8)) has a statistical meaning. In other words, $b_0^2 / \text{variance}(b) - 2$ represents a number of quanta which may be rearranged $\{b_0^2 / \text{variance}(b) - 2\}!$ ways to give an overall weight.

We suggest that one should use the factorial form ((8)) a priori to obtain the gamma function weight in $\int db F(b)$. If there is an additional Maxwell-Boltzmann weight linked with energy, i.e. $\exp(-bE)$ in each b region, then one has instead:

$$\int db F(b) \exp(-eb) \quad ((9))$$

Given the a priori form of $F(b)$ as a gamma function argument, one may insert it as such and obtain the following result for ((9))

$$\{1 - (1-q)e/T\}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)} \quad ((10))$$

In other words we suggest that there may be some statistical principle at work in the factorial expression ((8)) which may allow one to start with this factorial a priori to deduce other functions such as the Tsallis distribution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that (1) assigns the Tsallis distribution to describe an energy distribution in a space consisting of different equilibrium regions, each with its own temperature. (1) uses the a priori form of the Tsallis distribution and fits it to: $\int db F(b) \exp(-eb)$. Here $\exp(-eb)$ is the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann factor with $b=1/T$. Based on the mathematics of functions (i.e. a Mellin transformation), (1) suggests that $F(b)$ is the integrand of a Gamma function and chooses the appropriate values to reproduce: $\{1 - (1-q)e/T\}^{\text{power } 1/(1-q)}$.

We note that if instead of the MB factor $\exp(-eb)$, one has a uniform distribution, then $\int db F(b)$ would yield a factorial result if $F(b)$ is a gamma function integrand. A factorial result is a statistical counting value, i.e. it quantifies the number of permutations allowed. In fact, one has: $\{b_0/\text{variance}(b) - 2\}!$ where b_0 is $1/T_{ave}$. We suggest that there may be statistical relevance to this factorial. In particular, it may represent a statistical weight which may be used a priori. If that is the case, one would start a priori with the factorial expression and then convert it into a gamma function integral $\int F(b)db$. The next step would be to modify this by multiplying $F(b)$ by $\exp(-eb)$ to obtain the Tsallis distribution. In such a case, one is not fitting the known Tsallis distribution to a math function using a Mellin transformation, but is rather starting from a statistical factorial expression in order to derive the Tsallis distribution.

References

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